

Multi Label Text Classification

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Abstract

In this project, multi-label text classification task was to be solved by using different machine learning techniques on the restaurant review dataset. In addition to classical machine learning algorithms, different deep learning models and pretrained models were used, and the performances of these different models were compared and analyzed.

Index Terms: Natural Language Processing, Multi Label Text Classification, linguistics

1. Introduction

Multi-label classification allows classifying datasets with more than one category. In multi-label classification, there are several tags that are outputs for a particular prediction. During prediction, a given entry may belong to more than one tag.

For example, when guessing a particular category of movies, it could belong to horror, romance, adventure, action or all at once, so there are multiple tags that can be assigned to a particular movie.

On the other hand, in multiclass classification, an entry can belong to only one tag. For example, when predicting whether a particular image is of a cat or a dog, the output can be either a cat or a dog, but not both at the same time.

In this project, the multi-label text classification task was solved by using the Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis dataset, which was prepared based on the comments made by the customers.

1.1. Problem Description

Given a review from a restaurant, the system should automatically decide which categories of those reviews belong to. The number of different categories is fixed, and a comment can belong to zero, one or more categories. For instance:

- "I was very disappointed with this restaurant." → RESTAURANT//GENERAL.
- "I've asked a cart attendant for a lotus leaf wrapped rice and she replied back rice and just walked away." → SERVICE//GENERAL.
- "Chow fun was dry; pork shu mai was more than usually greasy and had to share a table with loud and rude family." → FOOD//QUALITY, AMBIENCE//GENERAL.

2. Theoretical Background

In order to solve this problem, the first thing to do is to encode the input review text and the output category. All the words belonging to the training set are combined, and a vocabulary dictionary is created, each review text can be encoded according to the ID number of the word in this vocabulary. This is the shortest and straight forward method. The same method can be

used for output categories, but category labels must be encoded as binary instead of ID numbers.

After the input and output values are encoded, different machine learning techniques can be used for the obtained mathematical statistics problem. Regression models can be applied, and the problem can be solved by accepting the categories above a certain threshold as 1, or directly several classification algorithms such as Decision Tree, KNeighbors etc. can be used. In addition to these models, deep learning techniques such as Convolutional and Recurrent Neural Networks can also be used to solve the problem.

In Multi Label Classification tasks, when neural network is used, softmax1 activation function is used in the last layer.

$$\text{Softmax}(x_i) = \frac{\exp(x_i)}{\sum_j \exp(x_j)}. \quad (1)$$

In Multi-Label classification tasks, the activation function in the last layer should be replaced with sigmoid 2 and the loss function with Binary Cross Entropy.

$$\text{Sigmoid}(z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-z)}. \quad (2)$$

In this project, to solve the problem, 5 different regressions, 5 different classification algorithms, as well as 4 different neural network architecture models were built, trained and their performances compared.

A model consisting of Conv1-D layers was built as the baseline neural network model. This model was trained for up to 15 epochs using the Adam optimizer and gave a f1-micro-avg result of 0.44 on the test set.

It has been proved that adding more layers to a Neural Network can make it more robust for different tasks. But it can also cause them to lose accuracy. That's where Residual Networks come into place. As it is known, it has been seen how useful residual networks[1, 2, 3, 4] are, such as image classification and object detection, especially in some tasks solved by using conv-2D. Therefore, the base Conv1-D model was developed by adding residual blocks with a similar logic.

As the third neural network model, a model consisting of Recurrent Neural Networks was built and trained. Finally, a merged model consisting of residual block convolutional layers and recurrent neural networks was developed and trained on the dataset.

All these neural models are produced and trained from scratch without using any pretrained model for feature extraction.

In addition to all these neural network models, the BERT[5] pretrained model was fine-tuned and trained according to the number of categories.

3. Methodology and Experimental Results

The restaurant review dataset studied on consists of a total of 2657 different elements, including 2000 trains and 657 test sets.

In this project, Scikit-learn[6, 7] library is used for regression and classification algorithms. First, 5 different regression algorithms were trained, and classification accuracy results were calculated according to the f1-average-micro metric. Then, the same process was applied on the classification algorithms. Among these algorithms, the best result was obtained with ExtraTrees[8] regression.

As a neural network model firstly, a base model consisting of 3 convolutional 1-D layers and 1 fully connected layer is built. In the last layer, the activation function Sigmoid is used. It is preferred as Adam Optimizer, this model has been trained for 15 epochs and the results shown in the table1 have been obtained. In order to improve the base model and achieve better results, residual blocks have been created inside the model. In total, 4 different blocks with the same structure are embedded in the model. This new model was trained with the same optimizer and loss function for 25 epochs, and a significant increase in f1 accuracy was observed.

After examining the results of the two models above, another model containing 1 recurrent (GRU) layer was established and trained with 20 epochs, and even better results were obtained than the convolution model consisting of residual blocks. At this point, considering that it would be logical to merge the convolutional layers with the recurrent layers, a final model was created, and this model was trained for 25 epochs, but no significant improvement was observed in the results.

Figure 1: Architectural structure of recurrent neural network model(Gated Recurrent Unit)[9] that has been built

The results on the test set obtained from the created models can be examined from the table1.

The results of neural network models showed that if there is not enough available data for training, the model may not work well for feature extraction and generalization. In order to eliminate such a problem, pretrained models can be used. At this point, the BERT model was accepted as a feature extractor and a hidden layer was added on top of it.

The established Base-Bert model was trained with 10 epochs and unfortunately no decrease in train and validation loss was observed. While investigating the source of the problem, the learning rate scheduler technique, which was examined in a different example, was used. In this technique, the learning rate is increased up to a certain point and then gradually decreased to 0. This technique is called warm up³. When

Table 1: Overall Results from all models

Model	F1-Micro-Avg
ExtraTreesRegressor	0.61
GradientBoostingRegressor	0.57
BaggingRegressor	0.57
RandomForestRegressor	0.60
AdaBoostRegressor	0.36
RidgeClassifier	0.59
ExtraTreesClassifier	0.44
DecisionTreeClassifier	0.45
KNeighborsClassifier	0.50
Base – ConvolutionalNetwork	0.44
ResidualConcolutionalNetwork	0.52
RecurrentNeuralNetwork(GRU)	0.54
Convolutional – RecurrentNetwork	0.54
BertNetwork	0.97

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
AMBIENCE#GENERAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	226
DRINKS#PRICES	1.00	0.10	0.18	20
DRINKS#QUALITY	0.88	0.80	0.84	46
DRINKS#STYLE_OPTIONS	0.60	0.30	0.40	30
FOOD#PRICES	0.92	0.88	0.90	82
FOOD#QUALITY	1.00	1.00	1.00	681
FOOD#STYLE_OPTIONS	1.00	0.98	0.99	128
LOCATION#GENERAL	1.00	0.04	0.07	28
RESTAURANT#GENERAL	1.00	0.99	0.99	421
RESTAURANT#MISCELLANEOUS	1.00	0.89	0.94	97
RESTAURANT#PRICES	1.00	0.91	0.95	80
SERVICE#GENERAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	419
micro avg	0.99	0.95	0.97	2258
macro avg	0.95	0.74	0.77	2258
weighted avg	0.99	0.95	0.96	2258
samples avg	0.83	0.82	0.83	2258

Figure 2: Detailed Bert model classification results on test set

this technique was applied, an incredible improvement in multi-label classification results² was observed and 0.97 f1-micro-avg results were obtained on the test set.

All codes are written in python using the PyTorch library and Quadro M 5200 Nvidia Laptop GPU is used for training time.

Figure 3: Learning rate change during training with 10 epochs on Bert model.

4. Conclusions

The results obtained in this project show that when looking for a solution to a given natural language processing task, instead of directly applying deep learning methods, classical machine learning algorithms can also give acceptable results. Another issue is that when the training data given is not enough, feature extraction using the pretrained model can provide very good results on the test set.

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6. References

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